

TECHNICAL TRAINING OF FOOTBALL PLAYERS AT THE INITIAL TRAINING STAGE

Amonturdiyev Bakhtiyor Kurbanovich

Professor of the Department of Physical Education and Sports
Games
Termez State University

Annotation: The article deals with the study of the dynamics and effectiveness of technical preparedness of young football players. The research was conducted among young football players in three stages. The study examined four age groups of football players. All participants received informed consent to participate in the study.

Key words: technical training, young football players, preparedness, testing, training, children.

Introduction. The level of modern football places high demands on various aspects of the training of football players, since the game has become more dynamic, interesting, and devoid of schematism [3, 4]. In connection with the emergence of new principles of playing the game, it is necessary to improve only the physical training of football players; significant attention must be paid to improving the technical and tactical training of football players [1, 2, 5]. During the match, players need to stop the ball, dribble, pass it, and shoot on goal. If the player does not perform these actions quickly and accurately, then the team wastes effort, which is a serious obstacle to success. That is why the effectiveness of his actions depends on how skillfully an athlete masters all the variety of technical means and how he applies them [6, 9, 10].

Since the process of technical training is the development of skills and abilities that ensure the effective use of the athlete's functional potential for the realization of high sports results in competitions, as well as systematic technical improvement

at different stages of training, coaches need to increase the effectiveness of training sessions precisely through the selection of rational means and methods of training [7, 8, 12, 19]. Exercises to improve technical training must be performed in extreme conditions and close to competitive activity. That is why football coaches must take these provisions into account and strive to improve the level of technical training of football players, taking into account the anatomical and functional features of the development of children's bodies and the features of the methodology for teaching technical techniques in football.

An analysis of literary sources shows that many studies on the problem of training football players have been carried out in elite sports. A number of scientific studies have addressed the issues of selection in football, development of motor qualities, improvement of technical and tactical training, and pedagogical control over the readiness of young football players [11, 13, 15, 20].

All actions of football players during the game are predominantly dynamic in nature, where the intensity of the work performed ranges from moderate to maximum, which places very high demands on the physical fitness of athletes [16, 21].

During the game, a football player must quickly and accurately perform all kinds of technical actions: stop the ball, dribble it, pass it, shoot at goal [17, 18, 22]. If the players do not perform these actions accurately and clearly, then the team, as a rule, does not achieve success.

So, the result of the team's actions as a whole depends on how well the football players master various technical means and how skillfully they use them during the game.

In order to achieve the desired result in the training process, it is necessary to constantly compare the planned growth of results with the actual one. This can be achieved using pedagogical control, using various tests and control exercises.

At the same time, the issue of optimizing the process of technical training of young football players at the initial stage of training, when the foundations of football

technology are laid, remains poorly studied. Therefore, the selection of effective means of sports training to improve the technical readiness of young football players is relevant.

The research was conducted among young football players in three stages. During the study, we examined four age groups of football players. All participants received informed consent to participate in the study.

At the first stage of the research, we conducted pedagogical testing. The studies were conducted during training. The results obtained showed a real picture of the level of technical preparedness of football players at the initial stage of training.

At the second stage, similar testing of the technical readiness of young football players was carried out in order to create a data array for analyzing the effectiveness of technical training in the annual training cycle.

At the third stage, pedagogical testing was carried out in order to generate an array of data on the level of development of technical readiness of football players in the annual training cycle. The test results showed the real state of the football players' technical preparedness.

To solve the set tasks, our research used methods of research and analysis of literary sources, and pedagogical testing.

The analysis of literary sources was carried out in the following areas:

- studying the features of technical training of football players;
- study of the structure of training football players;
- analysis of methods for teaching technical techniques in football;
- study of means and methods for developing the technical skills of football players.

The study of means and methods of technical training, as well as monitoring the technical readiness of football players, helped to identify the tendency to achieve high sports results.

The study of the literature on mathematical statistics and sports metrology contributed to a grounded approach to evaluating the results of the study.

Pedagogical testing was carried out using tests, according to generally accepted methods and recommendations in the methodological literature.

When determining specific tests to solve the assigned problems, we chose those tests that have found their use in the practice of training football players:

1. Juggling a ball. Stuffing was performed with the feet, thigh and head. Stuffing was performed in any sequence, without repeating it twice in a row. Only paddings performed in different ways were taken into account, including at least once with the head, right and left hips.
2. Hit the ball for accuracy. The kick was made on a stationary ball, with the right or left foot, from a distance of 11 meters from the goal. Football players direct the ball to a certain third of the goal vertically. Five kicks were performed with each leg in any way. The total number of hits was recorded.
3. Dribbling the ball around the posts and hitting the goal. Dribbling the ball, dribbling the risers and hitting the goal were carried out from the start line (30 meters from the penalty line): it was necessary to dribble the ball 20 meters, then circle four risers with a snake (the first riser is at a distance of 10 meters from the penalty area, and every 2 meters they place another three risers), and before reaching the penalty area, score the ball into the goal. The time is recorded from the start line until the ball crosses the goal. If the ball was not scored into the goal, the exercise was not counted. Three attempts were given, the best result was counted

During the process of pedagogical control, the trainer tried to get answers to the following questions:

- how do the planned changes in the technical readiness of players occur?;
- how to explain changes that were not planned, how to achieve the desired result?

In order to determine the level of technical preparedness of young football players, we conducted pedagogical testing, the results of which will allow us to determine its level.

It was possible to find out that with age the indicators of the studied qualities increase, but this process occurs differently at each age. Yes, the accuracy of hitting

a ball increases in the period from 7 years to 10 years by 0,5 times. At the same time, the maximum growth of the indicator occurs in the period from 8 years to 9 years, the indicator increases by 0,3 times, in the periods from 7 years to 8 years and from 9 years to 10 years the increase is 0,1 times.

Dribbling and shooting performance increases uniformly by 0,4 seconds at each age. The total increase in the indicator is 1,2 seconds. Ball juggling performance is also growing, but this process is happening unevenly. Thus, the maximum increase in the indicator was noted in the period from 8 years to 9 years - 2 times. In the periods from 7 years to 8 years and from 9 years to 10 years, growth is equal to one. The total growth of the indicator is four units.

Conclusions. Analysis of test results shows that the indicators of the studied qualities, which characterize the level of technical preparedness of football players, grow throughout the year, but this process occurs in different ways. The accuracy of a ball hit increases by only 0,5 times from 7 years to 10 years. The rate of dribbling the ball around the posts and hitting the goal increases by only 1,2 seconds. The juggling indicator increases in age by four units. In the annual training cycle, the studied indicators also undergo progressive changes - they increase throughout the year, but this process occurs rather unevenly. The rate of increase in ball impact accuracy is uneven and wave-like, the quality indicator is in the range of 4.9% - 10.5%. The rate of increase in dribbling is in the range of 2.2-5.5% and is also uneven and wave-like. The growth rate of ball juggling is quite high - 62.5% -44.4%, the nature of the change is uneven and wavy.

References:

1. Amonturdiyev, O. (2022). Voks sportining qirollari haqida. *Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры*, 2(12), 238-240.
2. Kurbanovich, A. B. (2022). Increasing physical culture and sports skills. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(4), 77-78.

3. Kurbonovich, A. O., & Narzulloyevich, S. R. (2019). Methods of organizing and conducting athletic training. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol*, 7(12).
4. Qurbonovich, A. O. (2022). Boks sport turida hozirgi kunga qadar bo'lgan o'zgarishlar. *Ta'lim va rivojlanish tahlili onlayn ilmiy jurnali*, 11-13.
5. Qurbonovich, A. O. (2021). Efforts for the Emergence and Development of Football Sports. *European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630)*, 11, 144-145.
6. Qurbonovich, B. A. (2021). Opportunities and Benefits of Football for Students. *European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630)*, 11, 112-113.
7. Qurbonovich, O. A. (2021). The role of physical education and steps in the formation of spiritual appearance in people. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(11), 710-712.
8. Yusupovich, R. S. (2023). Development of volleyball sport and its importance for athletes. *American Journal of Pedagogical and Educational Research*, 12, 134-135.
9. Rahmanov Shuhrat Yusupovich. (2023). Teaching how to play valleyball. *Open Access Repository*, 4(3), 595–598.
10. Yusupovich, R. S. (2022). Ozbekistonda gandbol sportining rivojlanishi va taraqqiyoti. *Ta'lim va rivojlanish tahlili onlayn ilmiy jurnali*, 16-18.
11. Rahmonov, S. (2022). Jismoniy madaniyatda shaxsni har tomonlama yetuk rivojlatirish. *Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры*, 2(12), 244-246.
12. Амонтурдиев, Б. К. (2022). Физическая активность как один из факторов здорового образа жизни и воспитания молодежи. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(7), 283-292.
13. Амонтурдиев, Б. К. (2020). Анализ разбора стиля игры команды для контратаки в футболе. *Вестник науки и образования*, (7-2 (85)), 60-62.

14. Амонтурдиев, Б. К. (2020). Роль планирования тренировочного процесса и мотивации на успешный результат чемпионата. *Достижения науки и образования*, (9 (63)), 50-53.
15. Бердиева, Х. К. (2018). Современный ценностный потенциал физической культуры и спорта и пути его освоения обществом и личностью. *Вопросы педагогики*, (3), 23-25.
16. Бердиева, Х. К. (2019). Теоретические основы развития ловкости у детей 6-7 лет посредством подвижных игр и игровых упражнений с мячом. *Вопросы педагогики*, (5-2), 43-47.
17. Бердиева, Х. К. (2022). Ҳаракатли ўйинлар-болалар жисмоний фаоллигини оширишининг муҳим воситаларидан биридир. *Экономика и социум*, (6-1 (97)), 433-437.
18. Хакназаров, К. К., & Бердиева, Х. К. (2019). Современный ценностный потенциал физической культуры и спорта и пути его освоения обществом и личностью. *Вопросы педагогики*, (2), 111-113.
19. Хакназаров, К. К. (2020). Факторы, определяющие физическое воздействие в игре баскетбол. *Достижения науки и образования*, (10 (64)), 53-55.
20. Хакназаров, К. К., & Бердиева, Х. К. (2019). Основы формирования культуры движений младших школьников. *Вопросы педагогики*, (4-2), 225-228.
21. Хакназаров, К. К., & Бердиева, Х. К. (2019). Физиологические особенности, влияющие на развитие силовых способностей учащихся старших классов. *Вопросы педагогики*, (5-2), 326-329.
22. Омонтурдиев, О. К. (2020). Значение физической культуры и спорта в создании крепкой семьи. *Достижения науки и образования*, (9 (63)), 53-55.